

Evaluation Methods Used for Distance Learning and Their Impacts on Academic Achievement: A comparative Study Between the Lower and Upper Classes (My Language " Curriculum " Is A Model)

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Abstract

This research aims to identify the most successful evaluation methods to be applied in the distance education, and their impacts on the academic achievement, comparing these methods in the lower and upper classrooms. The sample of this research is (90) Arabic language female teachers in the primary schools. The tool is the interview. The researcher applies the descriptive method on the collected data from the 20 electronic received interviews. The research's findings show the different aspects of evaluation affecting the distance education. The method of objective tests is one of the most effective methods. The research recommends providing the students with multiple choice questions, evaluated answers by computer applications. Also, the research recommends providing the students with right and wrong answers to identify their strengths and weaknesses. This type of questions helps the students to motivate their strength points and to improve their weaknesses points.

Introduction

In the light of what the world is going through due to the Corona virus pandemic, His Excellency the Minister of Education in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia (Dr. Hamad Muhammad Al Sheikh Al-Awdah) announced that for the first semester of 1441-1442 AH, the class study will be replaced by the distance learning for all levels of education and thus the Ministry sought to provide the best methods education and evaluation leading to raising student achievement in the primary stage, evaluation is not the result of the present, but rather an ancient process and is a basic process for any area of life that seeks to develop the individual and improve his conditions. The progress of nations is measured by the strength of their educational system, so the more effective the system, the higher the achievement of students and their efficiency and their contribution to the development of their society.

The primary school or any educational stage must make every effort to provide the best methods of evaluation, and to continuously motivate students to study to provide the best results. This is done in cooperation between the teacher and the student, and here we see the relationship of evaluation methods to the student's academic achievement.

Among the most important curricula in Saudi society are the Arabic language curricula, which is presented to the primary school students in the name of "my beautiful language". The Arabic language is not only a subject, but rather a means of studying other school subjects. If the best evaluation methods are followed to achieve the educational goals, the student will be able to master all other subjects. For this reason, the scholars chose the current topic of the research, which is entitled "**Evaluation methods used for distance learning and their impacts on academic achievement: a comparative study between the lower and upper classes (my language is a model)**".

Research problem

Each generation seeks to transmit cultural, social, ethical and religious values and customs to the next generation, meaning that in the past, education was entirely restricted to children's observation of the behavior of parents and their application of those behaviors.

Until the generations were keen, little by little, to transmit the heritage through writing, in order to preserve it from extinction, until the education system took its role in growing to become what it is now, as a result of the development that the whole world is witnessing.

In view of this development, it shall be noted that the conquest of technology in many different areas of life necessitated the human need to keep pace with that development and to integrate that technological development with the largest possible scope.

On the educational level, technological development has had a remarkable impact on the education process, and this development has brought about a vast change. Among the most prominent of these changes is the communications and information revolution and the multiple uses of technology it contains. This process may require a unique education that meets the student's needs and positively affects his educational outcome.

Therefore, the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia contributed to keeping its citizens abreast of this technological development in education, as it merged education and technology so that they became one system despite the difference in the remote between the teacher and the student, taking into account the progress of the education process according to its correct approach.

In light of all the aforementioned, our need to know the extent of the impact and success of this educational process has increased despite the development and discovery of evaluation methods that shall be followed and the purpose of the impact of those methods on primary grades students and their comparison with the higher grades, and the ability of these methods to achieve the desired goals of the educational process.

Research questions

Due to the expansion of the research community on all primary schools in the cities of the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, the research community has restricted to schools located in Jubail Governorate, which numbered twenty-two primary schools for boys and thirty-eight primary schools for girls.[1].

From the aforementioned, the study problem appears to us, which seeks to provide us with an adequate answer about what are the evaluation methods used for remote education and their impact on the academic achievement of students of higher grades, primary grades?

Thus, several questions branched out for us from this problem, which are:

1. What are the correct evaluation methods used for remote education that are suitable for primary school students in the Arabic language subject?
2. What are the implications for the academic achievement of remote education for primary school students in general?
3. What is the effectiveness of remote education in achieving the objectives of the educational process based on the different evaluation methods used?
4. What are the obstacles that face students of the primary and upper grades alike in teaching the Arabic language remotely?

Research objectives

The objective of this research is to:

1. An extrapolation of the most successful methods used in remote education for the primary and upper grades of the Arabic language subject.
2. Knowing the extent of the impact of remote evaluation methods on the achievement of students in primary and upper grades of the Arabic language subject.
3. Discovery of differences in academic achievement between the results of remote evaluation and traditional education for both the lower and upper grades in the Arabic language subject.
4. Identify the effectiveness of remote education in achieving educational goals based on the different evaluation methods for the Arabic language subject.
5. Identify the effectiveness of remote education in learning the Arabic language for primary and upper grades students.
6. An investigation of the obstacles that face students of the primary and upper grades alike in remote education.

Research importance

This paper is expected to contribute to:

Highlighting the strengths and weaknesses of the evaluation methods used in remote education for the Arabic language subject for primary school students; this results in suitable results for the competent authorities to choose the correct methods in that process.

Which in turn can avoid that educational gap between remote education and traditional education. Sometimes the curriculum is compatible with the uses of available remote education technology, and some studies have shown that the use of technology in remote education has increased students' motivation for education, and not all lessons. The introduction to remote education is appropriate, so standards shall be made to ensure that the information is received correctly [2].

It may benefit from those in charge of the educational process, especially the Arabic language curriculum developers, and it may be considered an addition to the educational library.

Research Methodology

The study has followed the descriptive approach based on data collection and analysis.

Characterization of the research community, its sample and method of selection

The research sample has represented in the Arabic language teachers for the primary stage in Jubail Industrial City, whose experience exceeds five years, and the total community was chosen as an intentional sample and their number reached 90 female teachers, and the interview was sent to them electronically via email and WhatsApp after taking permission from the university, and the education office to distribute the sample, and after alerting them More than once, the sample was chosen by 22% of the total community, which consisted of 20 female teachers, 10 female teachers from the upper wool and 10 female teachers from the lower grades.

Tool design stages (Interview)

The interview has designed electronically and consisted of open-ended questions, some of which were closed, and it was judged by a group of five university professors; Where their views have taken and work to amend what required amending.

Research limits

1. Objective limits: The "My Beautiful Language" curriculum is applied to all primary school grades in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia.
2. Spatial limits: Primary schools for girls in Jubail Industrial Governorate.
3. Time limits: The first semester of the academic year 1441-1442 AH
4. Human borders: Primary school parameters in Jubail Industrial City.
5. Research terms.
6. My Beautiful Language Curriculum.
7. (Al-Rumaih, 2019) defined the My Beautiful Language Curriculum as: The curriculum developed for the Arabic language approved by the Ministry of Education for the primary stage in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, with its objectives, content, strategies, means and activities, and evaluation methods, and the curriculum was formally applied in the school year (121/18 AH).
8. Arabic Language.
9. (Awad and Al-Bustami, 2015) defined language as: linguistics and its origin is a language (Loghah), so the letter(waw) was omitted and it was combined into languages(Loghaat), and Loghoon and Laghwo means pronunciation. And language idiomatically: it is a customary system based on symbols and sounds that people employ in communicating with each other, and in expressing their needs, thoughts and feelings, or it is those sounds produced by a person's speech apparatus so that the ear receives them and the human mind translates them into idiomatic connotations.
10. What is meant in this research is the Arabic language: it is the mother tongue of the people of the Arab world, as they use it in order to communicate and express their needs, whether through writing or voices.
11. Remote education.
12. (Al-Najm, 2019) defined education as one who taught, and taught him something as a teaching, so he learned, and from it the words of Allah Almighty: ((And Adam taught all the names, then he presented them to the angels, so he said, tell me the names of these if you are truthful)) (Al-Baqarah: 31]. As for contextual meaning, it is a hall dedicated to broadcasting live lessons and lectures via audio and video via the Internet, and students receive sciences that are far from them. Where you are in a city or perhaps another country. Students

benefit from these facilities and receive their lessons using various means of communication. These means may include, in their simple form, printed materials sent by mail, or they may include, in their elegant form, lectures sent by computer over the World Wide Web. What is meant by remote education in this research: An educational process in which the student and the teacher are separated either spatially or temporally, and they communicate through printed or electronic means, and it is easy to make available to all.

13. Methods of evaluation: (Melhem, 2017) defined evaluation in the language as indicating the value of a thing and amending or correcting what is crooked. As for the scientific definition, it is the process of preparing or planning on information that is useful in supplying or forming judgments that are used in making a better decision among many alternatives of the decisions, and that it is not an end in itself, but a means to an end.

14. What is meant by evaluation in this research: It is the basic process of measuring the extent to which goals have been achieved and strive to achieve them, and it is one of the foundations of teaching operations.

Previous studies

The issue of integrating modern technology in teaching Arabic to primary classes learners in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The two researchers, Prof. Wafa Hafez Asheish and a. Jamila Musaed Muhammad (2020, Wafaa-Jamila) a study that dealt with the issue of integrating modern technology in teaching Arabic to primary grades learners in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, and the descriptive survey method was used in the research. The study community consisted of supervisors and supervisors of Arabic language teaching in education departments and Arabic language teachers and teachers. The sample was formed. Out of 420 individuals.

Of them (270) female and male teachers of the Arabic language (120) and (30) supervisors specializing in teaching Arabic in universities and the result appeared in favor of supporters by 81%. The reasons for support are that technology provides a set of educational options, audio and video and self-evaluation tests, and the percentage of opponents is 19%. Their rejection of the unavailability of a integrated Arabic language curriculum based on modern technology.

The effect of using electronic evaluation mechanisms in accordance with comprehensive quality standards on the Blackboard e-learning platform on the level of performance in tests and trends for students of the remote education department at Jazan University - Saudi Arabia.

The results of Ibrahim Ahmed Ghashem (Ibrahim, 2019) study, which he conducted on a sample consisting of 60 students, divided into two experimental and control groups. The researcher also conducted an exploratory study to measure the validity and reliability of research tools on 40 students, and the results indicated the achievement of the goals that raised the achievement rate of students through Electronic tests.

Linguistic evaluation methods preferred by secondary school students and their compatibility with the methods used by their teachers.

Researcher Ahmed Al-Akhshmi (Al-Akhshmi-2019) conducted a study aimed at finding out the linguistic evaluation methods preferred by high school students and the methods used by Arabic language teachers to evaluate students' learning and their compatibility with the methods preferred by students. The researcher used a questionnaire applied to 310 secondary and third secondary school students. And 81 teachers and the results of the research showed that students prefer the method of objective tests with a high degree. The results also showed that Arabic teachers always use classroom discussion and often objective tests.

This means that there is a congruence between the students' preferences and the evaluation methods used by teachers. Remote learning Arabic language study.

Ahmed Arif Al Yassin (Ahmed, 2017) conducted a study under the subject of Arabic language education based on remote education as an educational innovation in the digital age (a case study in the Pisa course), (Surabia) the researcher used in his study qualitative research and the researcher here is the main tool for data collection He used the interview method, the observation method, and the document method, then the researcher analyzed the results through the inductive method, and the descriptive analytical method within eight weeks, and the result was the success of teaching the Arabic language remotely.

The effectiveness of using remote education in developing academic achievement and the trend towards remote education in the educational technology course of general diploma students, the one-year system, Industrial Education Division.

Hamdi Al-Bitar (Al-Bitar, 2016) conducted this study that aimed to identify the effectiveness of the use of remote education in the development of academic achievement, and the trend towards remote education in the education technology course among students of the general diploma, the one-year system, the Industrial Education Division, and the study sample was 32 students (General diploma) at the University of Assiut, Faculty of Education, and the study tools were a teacher's guide for the remote learner, a subject of education technology, an achievement test and a measure of the trend towards remote education. The study tools were applied before and after, and the result was the effectiveness of using remote education in developing academic

achievement and the trend towards remote education in the educational technology course, general diploma students have the one-year system, Industrial Education Division.

The effectiveness of a computer program in evaluating academic achievement for the sixth class of primary school.

The researcher Muhammad Ashawi (2015- Ashawi) conducted a study in which he employed the activity of an educational evaluation program produced by the researcher for the sixth grade of primary school in the language lesson, and the study sample consisted of 314 male and female students, and they were divided into two experimental and control groups using an experimental constructive approach. The study is to increase the academic achievement of Arabic language learners by computerized software among the students of the experimental sample compared to the control sample students that were evaluated in a traditional (paper) manner. Evaluating the use of virtual classrooms in remote education programs (Imam Muhammad Ibn Saud Islamic University as a model)

Researcher Al-Jawhara Al-Subaie (2015, Al-Subaie) conducted a study aimed at evaluating virtual classes in remote education programs at Imam Muhammad bin Saud Islamic University. In order to identify the negatives and positives of virtual classes from the students' point of view, the researcher used the Descriptive Survey Method (a questionnaire) and the sample consisted of 375 students who were randomly selected, and the results of the study were from the students' point of view for the virtual classes that it has many positives and few negatives. The extent of the contribution of educational technology to the remote education programs pursued in Sudanese universities via remote

Researcher Essam Al-Hassan (2014, Al-Hassan) conducted a study aimed at identifying the extent of the contribution of educational technology in its comprehensive concept to remote education programs in Sudanese universities, with all its single and mixed modes. The study community consists of professors who carry out academic support and the role of designer directed in Sudanese universities that follow the pattern Mixed universities are three universities: Sudan University of Science and Technology, Al-Zaeem Al-Azhari University, and Bakht Al-Reda University.

Monotype: Sudan Open University. The researcher used the descriptive and analytical approach through a questionnaire distributed to a sample of 152 randomly selected subjects. The results of the research were that universities that take the mixed pattern. The contribution of education technology is weak in terms of communicating information to the learner in his location, the extent of his interaction with it, and in terms of design. Academic courses as for the university that takes the monolithic mode, which was represented in the Open University of Sudan, it employed the foundations of educational technology and was more evident in educational practice.

The effectiveness of education through playing using the computer and its educational programs on the achievement and creative thinking of first-grade students in Riyadh: My beautiful language course as a model

A study by Basem Hakim (2012-Hakim) aimed to know the extent of the effectiveness of education through computer play and its educational programs on the achievement and creative thinking of first-grade students in Riyadh, My beautiful language curriculum as a model. The researcher used the experimental method for this study. The sample consisted of 59 students randomly from Rabei bin Amer Primary School in Riyadh, and the results of the research showed the effectiveness of the effect of games in developing and stimulating creativity.

Evaluating the cognitive competence of primary school teachers in the field of building objective achievement tests:

The researcher (Saed-2012) conducted a study aimed at knowing the level of proficiency of the primary school teacher for the adequacy of building objective achievement tests, where the researcher adopted the descriptive analytical evaluation approach and the research sample consisted of 82 teachers who were chosen as a random sample where the study tool was an objective test consisting of 40 questions from A multiple-choice type, and the result of the research was that there is weakness at the level of sample individuals in building objective achievement tests.

Investigating of the previous studies

This is an estimate as there are not enough previous studies similar to this topic in primary schools. Therefore, we believe that this research is recent in its kind.

Similarities between the current study and previous studies:

The current study was similar to the study of Ashish, Muhammad (2020) and Al-Akhshmi (2019) Al-Subaie (2015) and Al-Hassan (2014) in terms of the methodology of the study, and the current study was similar to the

study of Al Yassin (2017) in terms of the tool and the material, and with the study Saed (2012)) In terms of the academic stage, and with Hakim's study (2012) in terms of material. Some results were similar with all studies.

The differences between the current study and previous studies:

The current study disagreed with the study of Ghashim (2019), Al-Qahtani (2018), Al Yassin (2017), Al-Bitar (2016), Ashawi (2015) and Hakim (2012) in terms of the study methodology, as the current study differed with Ghashim (2019) and Al-Akhshmi (2019). Al-Qahtani (2018) Al-Yassin (2017), Al-Bitar (2016), Al-Subai'i (2015) and Al-Hassan (2014) in terms of the academic stage, and the current study also differed with the study of Al-Qahtani (2018) and Al-Bitar (2016) in terms of subject matter, and it differed with all studies in the study community and sample.

What distinguishes the current study from previous studies is that it focuses on primary school students that use the effect of remote education in teaching Arabic language and measuring its impact on academic achievement in Jubail Industrial City. It was also distinguished by comparing the impact of remote education on teaching Arabic and measuring this effect on Academic achievement between the lower and upper grades, and we find that the current study was distinguished among the studies related to this topic as the first study within the limits of female researchers' knowledge.

In the current study, the researchers benefited from previous studies through diversity in their knowledge of these studies in theory, how to prepare the study tool, how to choose the sample, and how to use statistical methods.

Theoretical framework

Assessment:

One of the important foundations in the educational process is evaluation. Because it shows whether the process is going as required or there is a defect in order to address and amend it, and it is the important way to achieve the desired goals.

The difference between assessment, measurement, and evaluation

People are always confused about the vocabulary of measurement, assessment, and evaluation, and that they have one meaning, but there is a difference between them. Measurement is intended to collect quantitative information and observations about the phenomenon in question using appropriate tools or measures such as tests, questionnaires, observation cards, measures of tendencies and trends, and it gives only a partial idea about a person because it deals with a specific aspect of it. Measurement is defined statistically as the quantitative assessment of objects or levels depending on that if anything exists, it exists in an amount and thus can be measured. As for evaluation, it is a process in which the data resulting from the measurement is used to make judgments about the phenomenon in question. For example, it is the process of issuing a judgment on what the learner knows based on his performance in an appropriate measurement tool, which is an achievement test in this case. As for assessment, it is a process in which the data resulting from the measurement is used to make judgments about the phenomenon subject of the evaluation and to make use of these judgments in taking appropriate decisions about the ways and means that can be followed in dealing with deficiencies, avoiding negatives, and overcoming difficulties. Through this, it is clear that the assessment process includes both measurement and evaluation, as they are two basic aspects on which the assessment process depends in collecting data and issuing judgments (Annab, 2015).

This is a simple example that helps distinguish between measurement, evaluation and assessment: the teacher uses the test as a measure and on the basis of which he gives a quantitative description or a numeric expression indicating the marks, so the teacher here made a measurement process and when he converts these numbers into estimates such as weak, fail, and recommends addressing weakness and avoiding deficiency Good, very good, excellent, for he has carried out the process of evaluating or consolidating the excellent results, this is the assessment, and it is clear from this that the assessment is more general and more comprehensive than evaluation and measurement, and that they are two parts of the evaluation, and the evaluation is broader than measurement because it depends on more methods than the measurement methods that are satisfied with it. The use of tests and examination (Abd al-Khaliq and Abu Diab, 2007).

Assessment objectives:

1. Knowing the extent to which the desired goals have been achieved
2. To make sure of the validity of the decisions that have been implemented, and to make the decision to complete or stop it and replace
3. Knowledge that enables teachers, administrators, and students

4. Help with statistics and accurate reporting
5. Putting the degree owed to learners
6. Identifying strengths and weaknesses (Melhem, 2017)
7. Provide information necessary to predict specific behavior in the future.

8. Helps the teacher judge the degree of adequacy of the teaching strategies, methods, and methods he practices (El-Arnousi et al., 2013)

The Assessment contains three types in terms of time, namely

A- Pre-Assessment:

Before starting the teaching process, the purpose of which is to diagnose, is to know the extent of the learner's readiness to learn (Al-Dossary, 2004) and to help link the previous information with the new lesson and assist in preparation as well.

B- Formative assessment:

This evaluation takes place during the learning process and is done periodically as it provides continuous information and aims to determine the effectiveness of learning methods and to identify strengths and weaknesses (Melhem, 2017).

C- Final Assessment:

It is conducted at the end of the lesson or at the end of the educational unit or at the end of the academic stage, and aims to measure the extent to which the objectives of the lesson, unit or stage of study have been achieved, so that it can determine and limit the student's gains after the completion of the teaching process, and the teacher informs of the goals that have been achieved and not achieved And making judgments about the effectiveness of the educational process. This results in transferring the student to higher academic levels, as well as granting scientific certificates at the end of the academic levels. (Nuri, 2015)

A practical example of an irregular plural lesson:

At the beginning of the lesson, students are asked about what the plural is and what has been presented previously, and the answer is made by combining the Sound of masculine plural and Sound feminine plural, and here is the pre-Assessment.

During the lesson, the teacher asks students to express a variety of words or provide an example of an irregular plural, or plural of a specific word and determining its type, and here is the formative assessment.

At the end of the unit, students are tested on all types of addition, and here is the final assessment.

Tests

Among the most important tools applied to collect data, make decisions, or form judgments and make decisions, tests are an organized procedure to measure a feature through a sample of behavior (Al-Melhem, 2017).

A- The first type is traditional tests that include oral and oral exams

B - The second type of objective and includes:

1. Multiple choice questions
2. True and false questions
3. Questions of marriage and matchmaking

Multiple Choice Questions:

It consists in giving a question in the form of a phrase, a sentence, or even a semi-sentence, then giving four or five answers, only one of which represents the correct answer, and among the most famous centers depending on this type of questions is the National Center for Measurement, and its advantages are:

1. Ease of use
2. It can be used in all fields of knowledge
3. The student's ability to distinguish the correct answer increases by remembering the material
4. High reliability
5. Easy to debug

Its disadvantages:

1. It requires more accuracy and time than other questions
2. Serendipity and speculation play a role
3. It is easy to cheat this type of question

True and False Questions:

A group of sentences, or phrases, some of which contain correct information from what the student studied in a subject, and others contain false information, then the student is asked to judge those statements whether they are true or false, and among its advantages:

1. Easy to debug.
2. The answer to this type of paragraphs can be estimated completely objectively.
3. The student can answer at a certain time a number of true and false paragraphs more than any type of other paragraphs.
4. Covering a large part of the course.
5. Although the time is equal in both cases, this means more comprehensive in terms of quantity.

Among its shortcomings:

1. Right and wrong clauses contain only two possible answers, one of which is the correct answer. The student who does not know the answer is allowed to choose the correct answer randomly.
2. Most of the paragraphs of right and wrong are related to simple facts and superficial information because it is difficult to design paragraphs of this type that are suitable for measuring understanding and application.

Mating Questions

This type is considered one of the most important and useful objective questions, given that the objective elements in it are widely available, and the reason for that is that the guesswork element in it is much less than in the “right and wrong” test, which increases the stability factor of this test, and its advantages:

1. Easy debugging
2. It helps to contain a large amount of homogeneous facts
3. It is useful for acquiring a large part of the general culture when the student remembers, for example, books and their authors
4. It helps students a lot in making them remember events and dates (Melhem, 2017)

Assessment methods in remote learning

In light of the shifts towards remote learning and social networking platforms, the evaluation process is no longer an end in itself to determine the success of learners, their transfers, and their progress through a set of electronic tests that focus on memorizing learners in order to form a vision about learners' learning. From the process of interaction during learning through these environments, directing, enhancing and correcting its course, and the most prominent of these methods are:

1. Written sheets on the web
2. Performance tasks
3. Games and simulations
4. Electronic conferences.
5. Thinking out loud
6. Threaded discussions on the Internet.
7. Presentations.
8. Video projects
9. Podcasts.
10. Individual and group interviews via the network
11. Electronic surveys
12. Electronic questionnaire
13. Electronic exhibitions
14. Self-evaluation
15. Peer assessment (Ihssan, 2016)

Primary education philosophy and objectives

The primary stage is considered the stage of development in the child's life, and the beginning of his graduation from concentration around himself, to openness to primary groups. Right belief, right attitudes, experiences, information, and skills. And if, according to educational scientists, life is a process of continuous adaptation, and it remains in harmony between the internal formative and external environmental factors, until it creates a coherent pattern from all of this, and if growth is the process of the evolution of the organism from the physical, intellectual and mental aspect, then it is assumed a process Education is to be based on the characteristics of the

stage in which the education takes place, where "education depends entirely on growth, meaning that education does not take place without being matched by progress in the growth process. This calls for saying that learning and growth are two interrelated factors, each affecting the Other." (Salem, 2008)

Hence, the philosophy and objectives of primary education cannot be defined independently of the nature of the learner's development. And that the educational policy pursued in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia, especially in primary education, is embodied through the tremendous efforts made for the benefit of this stage of education, and aims to achieve a set of objectives that can be summarized as follows (Ministry of Education, 2020):

1. Ensuring quality, equitable and inclusive education for all and promoting lifelong learning opportunities for all.
2. Improving teacher recruitment, qualification, and development.
3. Improving the educational environment that stimulates creativity and innovation.
4. Improving the financial efficiency of the education sector.
5. Development of curricula, teaching methods and evaluation.
6. Enhancing students' values and skills.
7. Enhancing the capacity of the education and training system to meet the requirements of development and the needs of the labor market.
8. Increase the participation of the private and private sectors in education and training.

The following are the general objectives of My Language (Arabic):

1. Preserving the tongue from error, keeping the pen from slipping, and forming sound language habits.
2. Familiarize students with the power of observation and rational logical thinking.
3. Raising the faculty of induction, judgment, justification, and other mental benefits that accrue to it to follow the method of induction in studying the rules.
4. Using grammar to understand the correct speech in a way that helps to quickly assimilate the meanings
5. Providing students with the ability to use grammar in different language situations.
6. Sharpening minds, refining taste, and developing the student's linguistic wealth.
7. That the student acquires the ability to recite recitation so that he utters the words correctly and performs the meanings well.
8. The student acquires the ability to read silently at an appropriate speed with an understanding of the main and subsidiary ideas.
9. Developing the abilities of good listening so that the student can focus attention on what he heard.
10. Developing the student's tendency to read and learn through free reading.
11. Gain a linguistic wealth by getting acquainted with new words.

E-learning: As the European Commissioner defined it, it is one of the concepts of the Internet space that often does not have a specific definition. The term e-learning does not agree on a specific definition for it. There is a broadening of the definition to include any education that takes place through electronic means: (radio, television, networks. ... etc.) and some of them were limited to networks. It was known that it is the use of new multimedia technologies and the Internet to improve the quality of education by facilitating access to resources and services in addition to remote cooperation and exchange, and Horton defined it comprehensively as "any use of web technology and the Internet to effect learning." And King Abdulaziz University knew it, and some considered it a form of remote education, as it was known as a method of learning using modern communication mechanisms such as computers, networks, multimedia, and Internet portals in order to deliver information to learners in the fastest time and at the lowest cost, and in a way that enables the educational process to be managed and controlled. Measuring and evaluating learners' performance.

Self-learning: It is a way to encourage individuals to become self-reliant learners, which relies mainly on self-reading programs. It is also known as the method that the individual himself uses in different educational situations to acquire information and skills, so that he moves from the focus of attention from the teacher to the learner, so the learner is the one who decides when and where it ends, and which means and alternatives he chooses, and then he becomes responsible for his learning and for making his cultural progress And on the decisions he makes (Atmizi, 1434)

Remote learning: UNESCO stated that remote education differs from traditional education in that it is based on the concept of self-learning, the employment of modern technological media in education, the absence of the teacher and the learner in one place or one time, and the learner not being devoted to study, as happens in traditional education. Remote education has been defined as the systematic use of printed and unprinted media that are well prepared in order to bridge the separation between learners and teachers, and to provide support to learners in their studies (Atmizi, 1434).

Remote education began in Saudi Arabia with the beginning of the new academic year 1442 AH, with the application of the remote education system to all schools and universities in the Kingdom, as a result of the spread of the Corona virus and its concern for the safety of citizens and the reduction of disease in the Kingdom, and it was 11/1/1442 AH interview to 30 / 8/2020 AD is the first day to start studying through the educational platforms accredited free of charge by the Ministry of Education, mainly on the “My School” platform, in addition to some auxiliary educational channels on the national education portal “Ain”, which also provides students with textbooks for all grades and stages, **Which aims to:**

1. Achieving the objectives of the Kingdom's vision of building a strong educational system. Inculcating the skills of sustainable education among students.
2. Preparing unprecedented educational programs on the Internet that contribute to developing the vision of remote education, or self-education that the Kingdom seeks.
3. Focusing on the student's skills, identifying individual differences between the student, and dealing with each one separately according to his interests and skills.
4. Seeking to train teachers to change the pattern of education and move away from traditional methods of teaching.
5. Relying on the skillful aspect of communicating information and moving away from the quantitative standard in entering information to students.
6. Focusing on teaching students the skills of cooperation and communication and instilling a sense of social responsibility in them.
7. Promoting the students' love of learning and erasing the negative idea that many students adopt about the educational process, which makes it one of the things that they do not enjoy doing.

And one of the most important general foundations on which education is based in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia is that the origin of education in all its subjects and all its stages is in the Arabic language, except when necessary, teaching it in another language. The language consists of four basic skills, which are the skill of listening, speaking, reading, and finally writing. We will learn about the following about each skill.

Firstly, listening: it is a complex skill in which the person listening gives the speaker all his attention, focuses his attention on his speech, and tries to interpret his voices and gestures, all his movements, and his stillness. In order to comprehend what is contained in the spoken message, in a manner that ensures the listener achieves good verbal communication with the other, or is the ability to understand and respond effectively to oral communication (Rashid Muhammad Attiyah Abu Sawaween, 2005). Listening is also defined as a sensory process based on the basis of distinguishing between different sounds, generating meanings and information, reminding and preparing them, or it is the mediation between sound and meaning, or it is an active dynamic sensory process for mental presence, understanding and interpretation of the hearing, responding to it, and expressing needs and attention. And information that the listener provides to other people (cheung, 2009).

(Sami Abdullah Rizk et al., 1393) refer to aspects that illustrate the importance of listening as follows:

- 1- The listening function in preserving and transmitting Arab and Islamic heritage.
- 2- Its function in the growth and transmission of the language.
- 3- His job in the educational side. His job in the cultural aspects.
- 4- Listening and the Holy Quran.

Secondly, speaking: it is a process by which sounds are produced in addition to the facial expressions accompanying the voice, which contribute to the process of interaction with listeners, and this process is a complex client that includes many systems, including: the phonemic, semantic and grammatical system; With the intention of transmitting an idea or feelings from the speaker to others (H.G. Widdowzon, 1978). (Robinson, 1988) defines it as the art of transmitting knowledge, experiences, and beliefs not only through the elements of verbal or verbal speech, but also through the use of language accompanying physical signs.

(Muhammad Rajab Fadlallah, 200) identified the importance of speaking about the benefits olifein general, including:

- 1- oral expression is important; Because we speak more than we read or write, and if a person hears what is equal to a book per day, then he speaks in a week equals writing, while in a month he reads what is equal to a book, and in the year he writes what equals a book.
- 2- If many people tend to receive the language by listening more than reading, they also prefer sending it more words than writing.
- 3- Oral expression is suitable for the learner and the illiterate, and it is an essential element of learning. Through it, the learner acquires information, and it is a means of understanding and understanding.
- 4- Oral expression is the means for the individual to express his feelings, opinions, and ideas, and hence it is the main form of communication.

5- Oral expression is important because of the multiplicity of areas of life that we need in selling and buying situations, meetings, and events, discussing issues, and solving problems.

6- Oral expression is a movement of the mind, a translation of its ideas and components, and training in language practice by formulating sentences, arranging elements, and using and pronouncing words.

7- Oral expression enables us to learn about other people's ideas and the results of their work, and know their opinions and trends in life, as it reflects the level of the individual's culture and the extent of his linguistic mastery.

8- Oral expression is the basis for communication of individuals and societies, and with the advancement of means of communication, its importance has increased, and its use has increased.

Third: Reading: (The Arabic Language Academy in Cairo, 2004) defined reading as a language that means annexation and plural, and from that the book was read and read in the Qur'an that follows its words given and uttered them and followed his words but did not utter them. It was recently called silent reading and reciting the verse from the Qur'an uttering its words out of consideration or from memorizing, so he is a reciter. As for the idiomatic meaning of the concept of reading, he defined it (Muhammad Salah al-Din Majar, 1971) as an intellectual and mental activity in which many factors are involved, whether on the part of the reader himself. Or, in terms of the environment, or the material being read and defined (Qurah, 161) as a process that includes proper verbal performance in addition to the reader's understanding of what he is reading, criticizing it, and translating it into behavior that solves a problem, or adds a new element to life's features.

Reading achieves many functions for both the individual and society

In terms of its importance to the individual and society:

- 1- A means of academic achievement in all academic subjects; Because it is a way to gain knowledge and information.
- 2- One of the most important windows of human knowledge.
- 3- A means of training scholars and innovators.
- 5- It increases the individual's experience in length, width, depth and breadth.
- 6- It is the locomotive of society for progress and advancement.
- 7- A means of social change.
- 8- A means of international rapprochement and global understanding.
- 9- One of the most important means of social communication.

Fourth: Writing: Al-Qalqashandi defined it (Al-Qalqashandi, 2000), that writing is a source language. Correct in grammar, and in a variety of methods, the horse group was told a battalion, and the mule was written if you combined its blades with a ring or belt or the like, and then the line was called a writing to collect the letters together, just as the village beads are writing to join some beads together, Ibn Al-Arabi said: The writing may be launched on knowledge, and from it the words of the Almighty (or they have the unseen, they write) that is, they know, but from writing idiomatically it is: a spiritual industry that appears with a gethsemene instrument indicating what is meant by the mediating of its systems. In himself, and the Gethsemene with the line drawn by the pen. (Ibn Khaldun in his introduction, 1974) stated that calligraphy and writing are human artefacts, and they are drawings and literal forms that indicate the audible words that refer to what is in the soul. He defined it (Walter J. Ong, 134, 17) as any visible or tangible sign that has a meaning of its own. He defined it (Mahmoud Al-Naqa, 2009) as a motor ability supported by a precise visual perception and a fixed mental perception of the form (line and dictation), and then a mental perception of the idea supported by a sound linguistic container and with the synergy of these components the individual learns to write.

The importance of writing is evident in that it is the combination of language arts, but rather that it requires all other skills, in speech or speech the listener can stop the speaker and ask him about something he did not understand, and he can ask him to repeat and repeat, moreover, speech and speech helps to understand its content using signs and expressions the face, body movements, and other things that help clarify and show the meaning, as for writing, it has special skills that are not found in any other art of language (Fathi Ali Younes, 2012)

Writing is one of the means of thinking, so a person thinks with his pen. Because he thinks while he writes, and in order to continue writing, the flow of ideas, the successive vision, his thoughts multiply and twist, branch, transcend and deepen, he writes any writing to think, and therefore thinking is clearly revealed in the symbols of the written words, and then writing becomes a way of thinking, through which the individual can distinguish between vague thinking and clear successful thinking (Mahmoud Kamel Al-Naga, 2008).

Presentation, discussion, and interpretation of results

Presentation of the result of the first question, which states: In your opinion, what are the correct assessment methods used in remote education that are suitable for students of the primary stage of the Arabic language subject.

Figure (1)

Figure (1) shows the respondents' response and opinion regarding the correct evaluation methods used in remote education, as the views of the subjects were divided into four sections, each of which was equal to the other.

Result presenting

It is noticeable in the above figure that the best assessment methods that the respondents chose according to their opinion is the assessment during the class through questions, reading and dictation, as it received 40% or 8 votes, and the short tests were equal to it by 80%, i.e. 8 votes, followed by learning by playing that scored 20%, i.e. voters, and the opinion of work papers and school homework was equal to him, as he won 20%, i.e., votes cast.

Discuss the result of the first question

The researcher Ahmed Al-Akhshmi has supported in his study (the preferred linguistic assesment methods of high school students and their compatibility with the methods used with their teachers) using the method of tests that won 40% of the respondents' opinions, as he mentioned in his research that students prefer the method of tests with a high degree

Researcher Ahmed Al-Qahtani has supported in his study (the effect of using formative evaluation methods on academic achievement in the science course of intermediate school students) by using the formative testing method, which won 40% of the respondents' opinions, as he mentioned in his research that the effect of using formative assessment methods increases Education maintenance level

It has contradicted Basem Hakim's study entitled (The Effectiveness of Education through Playing Using the Computer and its Educational Programs on Achievement and Creative Thinking of First Grade Students in Riyadh is in contradiction to the decision of My Beautiful Language), as the learning style by playing according to the opinion of the subjects obtained a small percentage of 10% only, and this contradicts the opinion of researcher Basem Hakim

The researchers believe that the result is satisfactory because constructive evaluation and short tests help to identify the strengths and weaknesses of the student. It also introduces the learner to the results of his learning and gives him an idea of his performance clearly, unlike learning by playing or working papers and assignments.

Presenting the result of the second question, which states: From your point of view, what are the implications for the academic achievement of remote education for primary school students in general?

Figure (2)

Figure (2) shows the respondents' responses and their opinion on these effects, and we can see the conflicting opinions, as 35% of the respondents believe that the educational, skill, and cognitive loss is the most severe impact on the educational process.

Result presenting

The above figure shows us the consensus of 7 of the respondents that remote education for primary school students results in a lack of educational skills and knowledge.

This is followed by the opinion of 5 of the respondents about the other negative impact of remote education, which constitutes 25%, which is a lack of a sense of responsibility for the educational process and partial dependence on the help of parents. Other opinions differed about the responsibility that rests with the teacher through assessing students individually and Questioning the accuracy of remote evaluation, and not developing the students' direct social and communicative skills.

One of the respondents pointed to a very important point, which is the difference in the intelligences of students according to the theory of multiple intelligences. Students with physical intelligence may constitute a defect in the course of this process for students with body-kinesthetic intelligence.

Discuss the result of the second question

It has contradicted the study of the researcher Muhammad Ashawi (2015 - Ashawi) entitled - The Effectiveness of a Computer Program in Evaluating the Academic Achievement of the Sixth Grade of Primary School - The negative impact on which 35% of our respondents agreed, which is the educational and skill loss that results from remote education, as it is divided 314 subjects were examined into two experimental and control samples, and the academic achievement of that experimental sample was remarkably advanced compared to the control sample without any educational or skill loss.

The researchers believe that remote education may be a major reason for the lack of educational skills and knowledge, as it does not fulfill all the desires and needs of children according to their stages of development.

Taking into account that education has positive aspects as well, which is mastering the use of modern technology, and it can also be the catalyst for students to rely on themselves and search for information clearly and correctly.

Presentation of the result of the third question, which stated: What methods can be followed in remote education to achieve the objectives of the educational process based on the different methods of assessment used?

Figure. (3)

Figure (3) shows the respondents' responses and their opinion on the methods used to achieve the objectives: 20% of the respondents supported the choice of motivational activities, and 20% of the respondents supported the choice of tests, 20% others of the respondents had the option to ask questions, and these options obtained the percentage. The highest, while the choice of the required duties and tasks got the least percentage of all the options, which is 5% that is, only one of the respondents supported that method.

Result presenting

It won equally the options for motivational activities, tests, and questioning, as each one of them won 4 votes from the respondents, followed by the option and diversification of strategies, where he won the percentage of 15% i.e. 3 votes, and with a difference of one vote comes the two options discussion and external applications, and in the last box of the voting gets the choice of the required assignments and tasks has obtained one votes, as we mentioned previously, 5% of those surveyed respondents

Discuss the result of the third question:

The study (2019, Ibrahim) confirmed that one of the best methods used in remote education are tests, depending on the results of the sample to which the investigative study was applied to 40 students, so the results indicated the achievement of the objectives that raised the achievement rate of students through electronic tests.

The results of the respondents agreed with the study (2019 - Al-Akhshmi) on the tendency of students and teachers to the method of exams, especially objective tests, and teachers' tendency to debate, but with fewer tests, based on the study. The results of the research showed that students prefer the method of objective tests with a high degree. The results also showed that teachers of the Arabic language always use classroom discussion and often objective tests, and it was within the study that one of the rarest methods used are the performance tasks.

It has confirmed the study (2012-Hakim) that one of the best methods is motivational activities such as games and competitions. The sample consisted of 59 students randomly from Rabi 'Bin Amer Primary School in Riyadh, and the results of the research showed the effectiveness of the effect of games in developing and stimulating creativity.

The researchers support these results and the options that are headed to it, which are motivational activities, because of the suitability of this method with the age group and the speed of their response to it, as well as the option to ask questions and tests because it is one of the approved methods and the most quality.

As for the choice of assignments and tasks required, it won a vote less than it deserved from the researchers' point of view, because this stage needs to apply what it has learned on its own, and this method enables to find pitfalls in achieving the educational goal.

Presenting the result of the fourth question, which states: What are the assessment methods that can be used in remote education in the lower classes (multiple choice).

Figure. (4)

Figure (4) shows the respondents' responses and their opinion on those methods, and opinions differed at that point by the respondents, as the multiple-choice option headed the methods with a rate of 95% or 19 votes, and the opposite is exactly the mating of two lists, where it got 20 Only%, that is, 4 out of 20 votes.

Result presenting

Although the majority supported the multiple choice, the choice of true and false also won a high vote with a difference of 4 surveyed people over the multiple-choice option, followed by the option to combine the word scattered letters with a difference of 3 respondents.

As for the syntax of scattered words, it got 8 votes, while the irregular word option got 7 votes and the continuation option came before the last by 25%.

And in the last place, the option of pairing two lists is 20%.

Discussing the result of the fourth question:

It has confirmed the study (2019-Al-Khashmi) that the most used assessment method is the objective test method (multiple choice). The results of the research also showed that students prefer the multiple-choice method and that it is one of the most successful methods.

And it has contradicted the study of (Saed-2012) that the teacher has a weakness in building objective tests

The researchers believe that the results were very fair, as multiple choice is appropriate for the age group (lower classes).

As it makes it easier for students to remember the correct answer among the answers

As is the case with the option of right and wrong, it helps in retrieving the information and remembering whether it is true or false only, with the option of combining the word scattered letters to the ratio of 60% due to the importance of mastering that skill at that age stage

Presentation of the result of the fifth question, which states: What assessment methods can be used in remote education in higher classes (multiple choice).

Figure. (5)

Figure (5) shows the respondents' responses and their opinion on those methods, and we see here that these methods change from the lower classes stage, where the choice of true and false won the highest vote of 90% and the choice of syntax the word from scattered letters was in the last place.

Result presenting

Although the majority supported the choice of true and false, the multiple choice also won a high vote with a difference of one vote over the choice of true and false, followed by the mating of two lists with a difference of three respondents.

As for the completing option, it won 12 votes, or 60%.

And in the pre-last rank comes the choice of the abnormal or irregular word with a percentage of 40% and is preceded by the option to compose the sentence scattered words with a difference of one examined in favor of the sentence scattered words.

And in the last place, the option to syntax a sentence of scattered letters is 20%.

Discussion of the result of the fifth question

Researcher Ahmed Al-Akshmi (2019 - Al-Akshmi) conducted a research entitled - The preferred linguistic evaluation methods of high school students and their compatibility with the methods used by their teachers - and that research supported the results of the subjects in our research, where 90% of them indicated the choice of right and wrong and on the other hand, researcher Ahmed Al-Akshmi's sample was the students' preference for objective tests with a large percentage.

The researchers believe that the syntax of the word scattered sentence is supposed to obtain the highest percentage, in order to match that skill with the age stage, unlike the lower grades stage, and that the ratio of the choice of marrying two lists has an acceptable percentage to meet it to measure the linking skill of students.

Presenting the sixth question, which stated: What are the formative assessment methods that can be used in remote education for the first classes? (Multiple-choice)

Figure (6)

Figure. (6) shows the respondents' responses and their opinion on the formative methods, and 80% of the respondents supported the choice of games and simulations, and this option won the highest percentage, while the electronic wall option and commenting on pictures won the lowest percentage of all the options, which are 10%, that is, only two respondents supported that method.

Result presenting

The games and simulations option won 16 votes from the subjects, followed equally by the performance and self-evaluation tasks option, where each of them got the same rate of 55%, 11 votes, and with a difference of 3 votes came the option to think out loud, followed by the option to think out loud the option of the blog vocalizations, as that option won 4 votes, i.e., 20% of the respondents supported that method. And in the last field of the vote, the electronic wall option and commenting on pictures gets only two votes, as we mentioned above, 10% of those surveyed.

Discussion of the result of the sixth question

Hakim's research (2012 - Hakim) supported the responses of the respondents who supported the choice of games and simulations. His study aimed to know the extent of the effectiveness of education through play, as his sample represented 59 students, and the results of the research appeared positive as the academic achievement of first-grade students increased through use this formative assessment method.

The researchers support these results and the presiding option for them is games and simulations. This is due to the suitability of this method with the age group and the speed of their response to it.

As for the podcast option, it won a vote less than it deserved from the researchers' point of view for the importance of activating that method for that age group, so that the teacher can measure several skills of that method, including the skill of speaking and pronouncing letters according to their correct articulation.

Presenting of the result of the seventh question, which states: What formative assessment methods can be used in remote education for higher classes?

Figure. (7)

Figure. (7) shows the respondents' responses and their opinion on the formative methods of the upper grades. 90% of the respondents supported the self-assessment option, and this option had the highest percentage, while the online discussion option was the lowest among all the options. It is 25% - that is, 5 of the respondents supported this method.

Result presenting

The self-assessment option received 18 votes by the subjects, followed by the peer evaluation option with a difference of 5 votes, and with a difference of only two votes from the peer evaluation, the electronic polls option came with an approval rating of 55% , and in the penultimate field the podcast option gets 30%, 6 votes in favor.

In the last column, 25% of respondents support online discussions.

Discussing the result of the seventh question

The results have opposed with the study (2019-Al-Akshmi), where classroom discussions were one of the most effective methods used by Arabic language teachers.

In the opinion of the researchers, the self-assessment option won the highest vote, due to the reason for its development of several aspects of the learner, including the aspect of independence, and it develops the cognitive ability of the student, and his participation in metacognition.

The second place is the peer assessment option due to the multiplicity of its positive points, including enabling students to work cooperatively and students' help each other.

It is worth noting that the option of threaded discussions on the Internet won only five votes. This is because it takes a longer time upon application.

Presenting of the result of the eighth question, which states: Through your experience, what are the obstacles that face students of the primary and upper classes alike in teaching the Arabic language remotely?

Figure (8)

Figure No. (8) shows the respondents' responses and their opinion on the obstacles facing primary school students in teaching the Arabic language. At the rate of 10% alike, which one of the subjects indicated that there are no obstacles, and the other subject indicated that one of the obstacles that impede the progress of this process is the lack of availability of hardware.

Result presenting

The first obstacle, which is the lack of writing and spelling skills, got the highest vote from the subjects, which is estimated to be 8 of the subjects, followed by that point 5 points, from whom each point got 20% i.e., two subjects for each point and they are: lack of time, difficulty in dealing with links Electronic, lack of motivation, lack of direct communication, technical problems, poor understanding of information.

And as mentioned - previously - the two points: there are no obstacles, the lack of devices, they take the last place in voting with one tester for each point.

Discussing the result of the eighth question

The researcher Al-Jawhara Al-Subaie (2015 - Al-Subaie) differed in her research - evaluating the use of virtual classrooms in remote education - as he explained the descriptive survey approach that she followed on his own eye, estimated at 375 random students, that the remote education process has several pros and few negatives, unlike our research sample. The subjects indicated that remote education has negative effects only.

The researchers see this point as a strength of support for the lack of spelling and written Arabic language skills, due to the importance of mastering it at that age stage, and through the modest experience of the students in field training, the choice of time constraints is a major obstacle during that educational process.

As for the opinion that states that there is no motivation, it is one of the obstacles that are difficult to deal with due to the need for direct communication between the teacher and the student and the need for the presence of body language between them to form a big difference for the student and his acceptance of the material.

The most important results of the research are that:

- 1- The assessment methods used to teach the Arabic language remotely are questions during class, reading, and dictation.
- 2- The assessment methods used for remote education for the lower classes of the test (multiple choice).
- 3- The methods used for remote education for higher classes are right and wrong.
- 4- Formative assessment methods for remote learning for the lower grades are play and simulation.
- 5- Formative assessment methods for remote learning for higher classes are self-evaluation.
- 6- One of the disadvantages of remote assessment is the loss of the skills side of primary school students, and one of its pluses is self-reliance in searching for information. And that is using modern technology.

7- One of the obstacles in using remote assessment methods is the lack of writing and reading skills.

Recommendations

- Proposing a ministerial program linked to the education platform (my school) to monitor students' performance during exams and continuous assessment to limit the high percentage of students' dependency on parents.
- Diversity in formative assessment methods for measuring skills from several aspects.
- Using the latest technological technologies to increase students' motivation towards learning and break the barrier of boredom during the class.
- Trying to limit the lack of educational skills for students through the diversification of evaluation methods. Including explanatory models for each program that is used by the teacher to avoid difficulty in dealing with new programs
- Diversifying the means of education used during the course according to the age group controls, in order to ensure that the information reaches the student correctly.
- Ensure that students are provided with evaluation methods in which the software is corrected automatically in the multiple-choice questions, and correctness and error, so that they can know their strengths and weaknesses and to see the strengths and motivate the student to continue as for weaknesses; It helps the student to improve his abilities.

The proposal is Conducting similar research to address educational problems and contribute to the educational process remotely in light of global crises and epidemics:

- The implications for student and teacher performance due to the Corona pandemic.
- The most suitable curriculum for primary schools' remote education.
- Measuring the ability of students and teachers in primary schools to learn from a remote.
- Educational aids suitable for remote education in primary schools.

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